

FINANCIAL DEVELOPMENT, GLOBALISATION AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Due to the increasing role of financial development (FD) and globalisation in economic growth over the decades and the current economic situation in Nigeria, investigating the contributions of FD and globalisation as well as their joint effect on economic growth, is very important for policymakers to formulate policies that can maximise their benefits for economic growth. Therefore, this study delves into the individual impacts of FD and globalisation, as well as their combined impact on economic growth in Nigeria. The study employed the ARDL model as well as FMOLS and Canonical Cointegration Regression (CCR) to analyse data from 1980 to 2023. The results from ARDL, FMOLS and CCR show that FD does not promote economic growth in Nigeria. Similarly, the study found that globalisation hinders Nigeria's economic growth. On the interaction term, the study found that globalisation enhanced the effect of FD on economic growth. It was also found that the labour force stimulated economic growth, while physical capital negatively impacted economic growth in Nigeria. Therefore, this study calls for policies on globalisation and the financial sector that will enable both to contribute optimally to the desired economic growth.

Keywords: globalisation, financial development, economic growth, ARDL, Nigeria

JEL Codes: F16; D53; O40; B40; O50

1. INTRODUCTION

Numerous studies have investigated the role of financial development (FD) in fostering economic development across various nations. Studies like Gizaw, Getachew and Mancha (2024); Fengju and Wubishet (2024); Meniago, Mazorodze and Mah (2025); and Diop et al. (2025) have documented the importance of FD to economic growth (EC). However, there is no consensus in the literature on the impact of FD on economic growth, as some studies found a positive relationship (e.g., Assefa and Mollick, 2017b; Bist, 2018; Meniago, Mazorodze and Mah, 2025), while some found a negative relationship (e.g., Adeniyi et al., 2015; Ductor and Grechyna, 2015). In relation to the lack of consensus in the literature and theoretical findings, some studies have started considering mediating variables in the connection between FD and economic growth. For example, Ductor and Grechyna (2015) and Akinlo (2021) considered the real sector as a mediating variable between FD and economic growth. Ibrahim and Alagidede (2018) considered human capital as a mediating variable, while Hausman et al.

(2005) and Meniago, Mazorodze and Mah (2025) considered institutional quality as an intermediate variable between FD and EC.

While studies have considered various intervention variables between FD and EC, this study observes that globalisation has been ignored as an intervention variable in the relationship between FD and EC. There is a connection between GL and FD, although the connection can be positive or negative. For instance, a financial system participating in financial GL is anticipated to have a high degree of FD, according to Gülcemal (2021), because financial GL will eliminate favourable and informal information in financial markets. Conflicts and heightened demands from foreign economic actors will cause the financial system to disseminate all available information. The best financial supervisory practices may spread and improve corporate governance as the financial system grows more globalised. As sharing of risks between local economic institutions and foreign organisations is possible in domestic and overseas exchange markets, financial GL promotes risk diversification. Therefore, a nation can borrow from and lend to foreigners during a recession, which lessens the fluctuating effects on investment, consumption, and income levels. International capital flows will facilitate global mobilisation and savings accumulation. Furthermore, financial GL lowers the international transaction cost and promotes a worldwide link between finance and the real sector, as stated by Tovar-Garcia (2012). In another way, Prasad, Rajan, and Subramanian (2007) stated that increased foreign capital inflows do not necessarily translate into greater EC because GL is closely linked to financial volatility. As is well known, uncertainty is significant in developing nations, and it may increase if they share risk. Financial integration does, however, also alter the value of steady-state capital holdings, which influences the spreading of risk among nations. Unless there is a capital constraint, countries whose economies are prone to risk will likewise face a drop in production and capital outflows as their prudential reserves are transferred to developed nations.

GL can boost the impact of FD on EC by attracting skilled labour, technology transfer and innovation into the financial sector and thereby spurring EC. Through GL, the financial sector can have access to external markets and capital, which can improve the efforts of financial institutions to make loans accessible for investment and hence promote EC. Similarly, the transfer of technology and innovation to the financial sector will improve the operational efficiency of financial institutions and reduce their cost of production, which will positively influence EC. However, the boosting of the financial sector by GL is not one-way traffic, as underdeveloped countries are not benefiting optimally from GL as EC is a concern compared to other developed countries. Yameogo et al. (2021) stated that most emerging countries are not reaping the benefits of GL like developed countries. This also limits the benefits the financial sector can gain from GL, which in turn might harm EC. GL can expose the financial sector of less-developed countries to global shocks and risks, as the financial sector of less-developed countries is underdeveloped, weak and has a small capital base, thereby hindering the financial sector from performing EC-enhancing functions.

Based on the argument above, there is a need to investigate how GL influences the connection between FD and EC in Nigeria. Therefore, the objective of this study is to examine the role of GL in the relationship between FD and economic growth in Nigeria. This study is essential given that Nigeria has participated in GL for decades, which is expected to promote national development. Similarly, in the last 20 years, the Nigerian financial industry has seen several policy reforms that are anticipated to boost EC by lowering information and transaction costs, increasing savings mobilisation, and extending lending to the private sector.

This study contributes in various ways. First, this study examines the direct connection of FD and GL to EC in Nigeria. Second, the study examines the combined effect of FD and GL on EC in Nigeria. Most of the previous studies considered other channels through which FD can enhance EC. However, the role of GL in the relationship between FD and economic in

Nigeria has not been exploited. This makes this study different from previous studies. Third, the use of a more comprehensive measure of GL, unlike most of the previous studies done in Nigeria. The previous studies used either trade openness, FDI, remittances, and official development assistance (ODA) as measures of GL, which can provide misleading results. This is due to the absence of policy features in these variables, which renders them unsuitable for providing a comprehensive assessment of GL. Consequently, the outcomes derived from these variables may hinder the expansion of policy acceptance and implementation. Three methods of analysis will be employed in this study. The autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model will be our main model to estimate the short and long run of the relationship, while the Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) and Canonical Cointegration Regression (CCR) will provide robust checks for the ARDL long-run estimates.

The study's remaining sections adhere to this arrangement. Section 2 provides the theoretical and literature review. Section 3 focuses on the methodology and data. Section 4 deals with empirical analysis. The study is concluded in Section 5.

2 EMPIRICAL LITERATURE

Empirically, evidence shows that some studies have examined the impact of FD and globalisation on economic growth individually or jointly. For instance, using ARDL, Baidoo et al. (2023) investigated how globalisation affected Ghana's economic growth and found that it had a negative short- and long-term impact on growth. Using panel ARDL, Hasan (2019) investigated how globalisation affected South Asian nations' economic growth between 1971 and 2014. The study found that while there was no short-term impact, globalisation in general, economic globalisation, and political globalisation all contribute to economic growth over the long term. Fosah et al. (2023) examine how globalisation affected the economic growth of 35 SSA nations between 1995 and 2018. Employing the Dynamic Common Correlated Effects (DCCE) estimation methodologies and the System Generalised Method of Moments (SGMM) techniques for the analysis, the study found a positive connection between globalisation and economic development. Kilic (2015) used the fixed effects least squares method and the Granger causality test to examine the effect of social and political globalisation on growth in a study consisting of 74 countries during 1981-2011. The findings show that aside from social globalisation, which has a negative effect on economic growth, other dimensions of globalisation have a positive impact on economic growth. Hordofa (2024) focused on Ethiopia's economy to examine the effect of different dimensions of globalisation on economic growth. Using ARDL as a method of analysis over the period 1981–2021, the study found that economic globalisation harms economic growth, political globalisation supports economic growth, and social globalisation produces mixed results in the long-run. Zhang et al. (2023) similarly investigated the dimensions of globalisation on economic growth-renewable consumption connection and found that political and economic dimensions of globalisation obstruct economic growth while social globalisation boosts economic growth.

There is conflicting evidence about the impact of FD on economic growth. While some studies showed a positive effect, others found a negative one. For example, in a study involving 74 countries from rich and developing countries between 1960 and 1995, Beck et al. (2000) reported a positive association between FD and economic growth. Using fully modified ordinary least squares (FMOLS) and dynamic ordinary least squares (DOLS) to examine the relationship between FD and economic growth in South Asian economies from 2000 to 2018, Ahmed et al. (2022) showed that FD boosted economic growth. Some of other studies (e.g., Schumpeter, 1911; King and Levine 1993a, b; Beck and Levine, 2004; Bist, 2018) established a positive connection between FD and economic growth.

Among the studies that found that negative connection is Iheanacho (2016) who showed a short-term negative relationship between FD and economic growth in Nigeria between 1981

and 2011. Using annual data from 1960 to 2010, Adeniyi et al. (2015) found a negative link between FD and economic growth in Nigeria. When the squared terms of FD were added to the model, however, the negative sign was changed. Using linear and threshold regression, Akinlo (2021) discovered that FD had a detrimental effect on economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa between 1986 and 2015. Using panel data from 52 middle-income nations, Samargandi et al. (2015) found an adverse relationship between FD in upper middle-income countries. Other studies (e.g., IMF, 2012; Ductor and Grechyna, 2015; Allen et al., 2014; Singh et al., 2023) found a negative association between FD and economic growth.

Some studies examined the effect of FD and globalisation on economic growth in the same study, though they did not consider the interaction effect. For instance, Elfaki and Ahmed (2024) investigated the contribution of globalisation and FD to economic growth in Sudan for the period 1978–2021. Using the ARDL model, the study found a positive effect of globalisation on economic growth, while FD harms economic growth in the long run. Kazar and Kazar (2016) considered the effect of FD and globalisation on economic growth among income groups in non-OECD and OECD countries using panel OLS. The study found that FD promotes economic growth in high-income countries in non-OECD and OECD member countries. Similarly, it contributes to growth in upper-middle-income and lower-middle-income countries, while it negatively impacts economic growth in low-income countries. Political globalisation promotes growth in high-income OECD countries, upper-middle-income countries and lower-middle-income countries. Economic globalisation boosts economic growth in lower-middle-income countries and low-income countries. Fuinhas, Marques and Lopes (2019) investigated how financial market development and globalisation impact economic growth in ten countries from 1980 to 2015 using the ARDL bounds test approach. The results showed that banking sector development stimulates economic growth both in the short- and long-run while stock market development enhances economic growth in the long-run only. The globalisation index indicators *de facto* and *de jure* have a significant effect on economic growth. Similarly, political globalisation and *de jure* contribute to economic growth in the long-term and financial globalisation and *de facto* boost growth in the short-term.

It is clear that many empirical research has investigated the connection between FD, GL and EC, either independently or in combination. However, studies have overlooked how FD and GL interact to affect EC. Therefore, this study intends to close this gap in the literature. The hypothesis is stated as follows:

H1. Financial development augments globalisation to impact EC in Nigeria positively

3 METHODOLOGY AND DATA

3.1 Theoretical Framework

The Neoclassical growth theory was first developed by Frank Ramsey in the 1920s, but its popular version was put forth by Robert Solow and Trevor Swan in the 1956. According to this theory, technology change has a major influence on economic growth, and that economic growth will not continue unless there are advances in technology. Solow and Swan codified a model which involved a series of equations which showed the relationship between labour-time, capital goods, output, and investment. The model assumes that countries use their resources efficiently and that there are diminishing returns to capital and labour. From these two premises, the neoclassical model makes three important predictions. First, increasing capital relative to labour creates economic growth, since people can be more productive given more capital. Second, poor countries with less capital per person will grow faster because each investment in capital will produce a higher return than rich countries with ample capital. Third, because of diminishing returns to capital, economies will eventually reach a point at which any increase in capital will no longer create economic growth. This point is called a steady state.

The model also notes that countries can overcome this steady state and continue growing by inventing new technology. In the long run, output per capita depends on the rate of saving, but the rate of output growth should be equal for any saving rate. In this model, the process by which countries continue growing despite the diminishing returns is exogenous and represents the creation of new technology that allows production with fewer resources. As technology improves, the steady state level of capital increases, and the country invests and grows. The neoclassical growth model output, as put forward by Solow and Swan is

$$Y = A K^\alpha L^{1-\alpha} \tag{1}$$

where Y = output, A = technology, L = labor, K = capital stock, α = elasticity coefficient

But Solow’s model of economic growth is based on the premises that output in an economy is produced by a combination of labour (L) and capital (K), under constant returns, so that doubling inputs results in doubling output. Contemporary versions distinguish between physical and human capital.

3.2 Model Specification

In accordance with a study by Ehigiamusoe (2022) and the growth model by Solow (1956), which links production to labour, capital, and technological improvement, this study provides equation (1). According to the model, labour, the buildup of capital, and labour-enhancing technology that raises productivity are the major promoters of long-term growth (Solow, 1956).

$$Y_t = A_t K_t^{\alpha_1} L_t^{\alpha_2} \tag{2}$$

where Y is the EC, K represents the capital. L stands for labour and A represents technological progress. The capital and labour elasticities are represented by α_1 and α_2 respectively while the time component is represented by t, while

$$\ln Y_t = \ln A_t + \alpha_1 \ln K_t + \alpha_2 \ln L_t \tag{3}$$

In addition to human and physical capital, other factors also impact EC during a specific time period; these are all summed up in A (Solow residual). Specifically, as stated by Ductor and Grechyna (2013), it could reflect the state of technical advancement of the economy, the level of financial development in the economy, and the quality of institutions, while Baidoo et al. (2023) stated that economic globalisation can influence (A_t). Based on these arguments, it can be divided into two parts as follows:

$$\ln A_t = \ln FD_t + \ln GL_t \tag{4}$$

By substituting equation 4 into equation 3, it becomes

$$\ln Y_t = \ln FD_t + \ln GL_t + \alpha_1 \ln K_t + \alpha_2 \ln L_t \tag{5}$$

where ln is the natural logarithm, GL is the globalisation and FD represents financial development, while other variables are as earlier defined. However, since this study intends to examine the interaction effect of FD and globalisation on EC, the interaction term (FD) is incorporated into equation (5) to become:

$$\ln Y_t = \ln FD_t + \ln GL_t + \alpha_1 \ln K_t + \alpha_2 \ln L_t + \ln (FD_t \times GL_t) \tag{6}$$

Studies like Ehigiamusoe (2022) and Akinlo (2024) have emphasised that inflation is relevant to EC of developing countries. By adding inflation (INF) as the control variable to equation 6 and expressing it in econometric form, it becomes

$$\ln Y_t = \rho + \alpha_1 \ln K_t + \alpha_2 \ln L_t + \beta_1 \ln FD_t + \beta_2 \ln GL_t + \beta_3 \ln (FD_t \times GL_t) + \beta_4 INF_t + \mu_t \tag{7}$$

3.3 Data

The period of this study spans the period from 1980 to 2023. This period is selected due to data availability. The GDP per capita (2015 US constant), which is the dependent variable, is used to measure EC. The study employs gross fixed capital formation (GCF) to proxy physical capital. The GCF is expressed as % GDP. Labour is measured by the total labour force. The labour force employed in this study consists of all the individuals who are 15 years and above who engage in economic activities to produce goods and services through the supply of labour. FD is measured by the financial development index from the IMF. The FD index from IMF is more comprehensive as nine indices are used to generate its financial development index (FD index), which summarises the depth, accessibility, and efficiency of financial markets and financial institutions. All the nine indices are then combined to form a single overall index of financial development. Globalisation is captured by the KOF Globalisation Index. The calculation of the overall KOF Globalisation Index is based on the average of the de facto and the de jure Globalisation Index. The inflation rate captured the consumer price index. All the variables are in logarithmic form except inflation. Data on GDP per capita, physical capital, labour force and inflation are obtained from the World Development Indicator, while globalisation index data is obtained from the KOF globalisation database of the Swiss Economic Institute.

3.4 Estimation Strategy

To investigate the individual effect of FD and GL and their joint impact on EC, the study adopts the ARDL model and the ECM developed by Pesaran et al. (2001), while the FMOLS and CCR provide robust checks for the ARDL long-run estimates. However, before ARDL estimation, the study engaged Phillips-Perron (PP) (1988) and Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) (1979) to obtain the stationarity of the variables employed. This study prefers the ARDL model proposed by Pesaran et al. (2001) due to some advantages. For instance, the ARDL model can provide results for both short-and long-run associations between dependent and independent variables. Also, the ARDL model can produce reliable results for variables with the same order of integration (i.e., either all the variables are I(0) or I(1)) and can also produce efficient results when variables with different orders of integration are combined, provided that none of the variables is I(2). Similarly, according to Pesaran et al. (2001) and Duodu and Baidoo (2022), the ARDL model produces more efficient results than ordinary least squares and other methods regarding data with a small sample size.

After determining the stationarity of the variables, the ARDL formulation of equation (7), which generates results for both long and short terms in a single equation as presented in equation (8), is estimated.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \ln Y_t = & \Phi_0 + \Phi_1 \ln Y_{t-1} + \alpha_1 \ln K_{t-1} + \alpha_2 \ln L_{t-1} + \beta_1 \ln FD_{t-1} + \beta_2 \ln GL_{t-1} + \\ & \beta_3 \ln (FD_{t-1} \times GL_{t-1}) + \beta_4 \ln INF_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^t \delta_1 \Delta \ln Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^u \delta_2 \Delta \ln K_{t-i} + \\ & \sum_{i=0}^v \delta_3 \Delta \ln L_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^w \delta_4 \Delta \ln FD_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^x \delta_5 \Delta \ln GL_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^y \delta_6 \Delta \ln (FD_{t-i} \times GL_{t-1}) + \\ & \sum_{i=0}^z \delta_7 \Delta \ln INF_{t-i} \\ & + \mu_t \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

From equation 8, Φ_0 stands for the constant term, while Δ is the first difference operator. t, u, v, w, x, y and z represent the optimal lag length for the variables. $\Phi_1, \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ and β_4 indicate the long-run coefficients. $\delta_1, \delta_2, \delta_3, \delta_4, \delta_5, \delta_6$ and δ_7 are the short-run coefficients while μ_t is the error term. Regarding the a priori expectations of the variables, FD is anticipated to boost EC. GL is anticipated to have a negative influence on EC in Nigeria. Physical and labour are expected to boost EC due to the important roles they are playing in EC.

Inflation is expected to harm EC in Nigeria due to an increase in the inflation rate. To verify the existence of long-run connections among the selected variables, Pesaran et al. (2001) introduced the F-test to determine if the lagged values of the variables in equation (8) are jointly significant. The null hypothesis, according to which there is no long-term association [$H_0: \phi_1 = \alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = \beta_1 \dots \beta_4 = 0$] against the alternate hypothesis of the presence of a long-run [$H_1: \phi_1 \neq \alpha_1 \neq \alpha_2 \neq \beta_1 \dots \neq \beta_4 \neq 0$]. Based on the F-test, a lower [$I(0)$] and upper [$I(0)$] bounds as two critical bounds were proposed by Pesaran et al. (2001). When the F-test is bigger than the upper critical value, then the null hypothesis is rejected, but when the F-test falls between the lower critical and upper critical value, the decision on the presence of a long-run relationship becomes inconclusive. However, when the F-test is smaller compared to the lower critical value, then the conclusion will be that the long-run relationship does not exist as the null hypothesis is accepted. Equation 9 specifies the ECM to be applied in the estimation of the short-run relationships as follows:

$$\Delta \ln Y_t = \sum_{i=1}^m \delta_1 \Delta \ln Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \delta_2 \Delta \ln K_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^o \delta_3 \Delta \ln L_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^p \delta_4 \Delta \ln FD_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \delta_5 \Delta \ln GL_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^r \delta_6 \Delta \ln (FD_{t-i} \times GL_{t-1}) + \sum_{i=0}^s \delta_7 \Delta \ln INF_{t-i} + \gamma_1 ECM_{t-i} + \mu_t \quad 9$$

To avoid econometric issues in the estimated results, the study executes some diagnostic tests such as the Ramsey reset, the autocorrelation test and the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey tests (BPG). Finally, plots of the cumulative sum (CUSUM) and cumulative sum of squares (CUSUMSQ) are used to assess how stable the model is. Aside from using the ARDL estimation technique, the study employs the FMOLS and CCR estimators to serve as robustness checks for estimated long-run results. Phillips and Hansen (1990) developed FMOLS regression in order to obtain optimal estimates of cointegrating regressions. The technique adjusts the least squares to take into consideration endogeneity in the regressors that arises due to the existence of a cointegrating relationship as well as serial correlation effects. Similarly, Montalvo (1995) asserts that the CCR estimator relies on transforming the cointegrating regression's variables in order to remove the OLS estimator's second-order bias. These methods are appropriate for estimating the long-run relationship between EC, FD and globalisation, and also the joint effect of FD and globalisation on EC, as they are capable of producing reliable results by properly addressing the issue of endogeneity.

4 EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

4.1 Descriptive Statistic

The descriptive statistics of the variables are shown in Table 1. The average value of inflation is 18.9491, which is the highest among the variables. This suggests that inflation is high during the study period. The average GDP per capita is 3.2656 during the study period. The FD index has the smallest average, 0.2079, which indicates a low contribution to GDP. The averages of globalisation, labour and physical capital are 1.6706, 1.4954 and 1.4383, respectively. All the means of the variables lie between the smallest and highest values, which confirms the consistency of the variables. The standard deviation of the series is less than 1 except for inflation. The FD index has the smallest standard deviation, and next to it is globalisation, while GDP per capita follows. This suggests that the variables show minimal deviation from their means. Most of the variables are positively skewed, as only globalisation and physical capital are negatively skewed. Regarding the distribution, the Jarque-Bera probability indicates that all variables – aside from inflation – are normally distributed.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics

	lnY	lnK	lnL	lnFD INDEX	lnGL	INF
Mean	3.2656	1.4383	1.4954	0.2079	1.6706	18.9491
Median	3.2289	1.4451	1.4727	0.2141	1.6883	12.8766
Maximum	3.4281	1.7399	1.7394	0.2908	1.7559	72.8355
Minimum	3.1487	1.0553	1.2408	0.1300	1.5556	5.3881
Std. Dev.	0.1031	0.1928	0.1224	0.0409	0.0699	16.6594
Skewness	0.3233	-0.2292	0.1904	0.1733	-0.3338	1.8542
Kurtosis	1.4427	1.9289	1.9138	2.5692	1.5983	5.3065
Jarque-Bera	4.8574	2.3186	2.2629	0.3695	4.1179	32.5809
Probability	0.0882	0.3137	0.3225	0.8313	0.1276	0.0000
Sum	133.8908	58.9701	61.3111	6.0275	68.4941	776.9110
Observations	41	41	41	41	41	41

4.2 Unit Root Results

Investigating the unit roots of the variables has to be done before moving on to the boundaries test for cointegration. This is essential to make sure that no I(2) variable is included in the study. This test has been performed under the models with no constant and no trend and intercept for the level series and for the series in first difference. Table 2 contains the unit root test results. The PP results indicate that only inflation is stationary at level, while all other variables are stationary at the first difference. According to ADF results, none of the variables are stationary at level, but they are all stationary at the first difference. The SIC is used as the basis for the selection of the optimal lag for the unit root test and 3 is used as the maximum lag length. Based on the unit root results, the study can confirm that no I(2) variable is included in this study, which shows that the ARDL model is suitable for the study.

Table 2 Unit Root test Results

Variables	PP		ADF	
	Level	First Diff.	Level	First Diff.
lnY	0.1756 (0.7323)	-4.5325*** (0.0000)	1.1925 (0.9376)	-3.2699*** (0.0000)
lnK	-0.2159 (0.6022)	-9.1815*** (0.0000)	-0.2769 (0.5700)	-5.9830*** (0.0000)
lnL	-1.4638 (0.9623)	-4.5859*** (0.0000)	2.0194 (0.9883)	-4.6367*** (0.000)
lnFD INDEX	0.0923 (0.7087)	-8.1785*** (0.0000)	-1.0267 (0.6681)	-8.1899*** (0.0000)
lnGL	1.2851 (0.9472)	-5.6726*** (0.0000)	1.3620 (0.9542)	-5.6725*** (0.0000)
INF	-1.6782* (0.0878)	-12.6365*** (0.0000)	-1.1917 (0.2097)	- 6.1980*** (0.0000)

Note: *, implies 10% significance, ** implies 5% significance and *** implies 1% significance. The values in brackets are p-values.

4.3 Cointegration Results

This study is not only concerned with the short-run connection between EC, the FD index and globalisation, but also interested in estimating the long-run connections between the variables. Therefore, there is a need for the variables to be cointegrated. To establish if

cointegration exists, this study engaged an ARDL-bound cointegration test, and Table 3 presents the results of the cointegration test. Because the F-statistic (7.8109) is higher than the upper threshold values at the 1%, 5%, and 10% significance levels, the results in Table 3 show that the null hypothesis of no cointegration is rejected. To ascertain the long-term and short-term relationships between the variables, the study can then move forward with estimating the ARDL model.

Table 3 Cointegration Results

F-Bond test		Null Hypothesis: No levels of relationship		
Test Statistic	Value	Significance	I(0)	I(1)
F-Statistics	7.7492	1%	2.88	3.99
K	6	5%	2.27	3.28
		10%	1.99	2.94

4.4 The ARDL estimation Results

Table 4 displays the estimated ARDL results and the results of FMOLS and CCR engaged to provide robust checks for the ARDL long-run estimations. The long-run results from ARDL, FMOLS and CCR confirm that physical capital harms EC, as its coefficient is significant and negative. This is consistent with Abdur-raheem et al. (2025) who found that physical capital has a negative impact on economic growth in Nigeria. The coefficient of the labour force is insignificant in the long-run ARDL, but it is statistically significant in FMOLS and CCR estimations. This indicates that labour contributes to EC in the long-run according to FMOLS and CCR results. The FD index impedes EC across the estimations, as its coefficient is negative and significant. GL insignificantly impacts EC in ARDL estimation. However, the coefficient of GL is significantly negative in FMOLS and CCR estimations. This suggests there is a negative connection between GL and EC. The interaction of the FD index and GL improves EC in Nigeria in the long-run based on the results from ARDL, FMOLS and CCR. The positive and significant coefficient of the interaction term implies that FD and GL perform a complementary role in the economy. Similarly, inflation enhances EC in the long-run based on the ARDL estimation, but the coefficient of inflation is insignificant in FMOLS and CCR estimations during the study period.

Table 4 The Long-Run Results of ARDL, FMOLS and CCR

Variable	ARDL		FMOLS		CCR	
	Coeff	Prob	Coeff	Prob	Coeff	Prob
C	2.6460*	0.0698	4.8197***	0.0032	5.0702***	0.0076
LnK	-0.1250*	0.0725	-0.1077***	0.0063	-0.1205***	0.0093
lnL	0.2206	0.3420	0.5561***	0.0006	0.5489***	0.0030
lnFDINDEX	-15.6432*	0.0629	-32.5992***	0.0000	-33.5319***	0.0000
lnGL	-0.5114	0.6972	-3.3860***	0.0002	-3.4961***	0.0000
lnFDINDEX*lnGL	9.3494*	0.0582	19.4096***	0.0000	19.9719***	0.0000
INF	0.0008**	0.0420	-6.22E-05	0.9788	-0.0001	0.8186

R^2			0.9183		0.9141	
Adjusted R^2			0.9034		0.8985	

Note: *, implies 10% significance, ** implies 5% significance and *** implies 1% significance. The values in brackets are p-values

For the short-run estimation, the optimum lag length was determined using the Schwarz Bayesian Criterion (SBC), which was employed after imposing a maximum of 4 lags on the variables level. In Table 5, the automatically selected lagged level of variables in the ARDL model is (3, 4, 4, 2, 4, 3, 1). The short-run result indicates that the coefficients of physical capital, labour and inflation are insignificant. Ashakah and Akpughe (2021) and Emiola and Fagbohun (2021) found an insignificant impact of human capital on economic growth in the short-run. The insignificant effect of inflation on economic growth is in line with Bolaji and Anyanwu (2025) and Ibrahim and Okoh (2021). The FD index and GL impede EC, as their coefficients are negative and significant at 1% and 5%, respectively. The interaction of the FD index and GL promotes EC in Nigeria. This suggests that the GL and FD index work together to support Nigeria's EC. The negative and significant coefficient of the ECM_{-1} indicates that long-term adjustments will be made by 0.9484% annually.

Table 5 The Short-run Results of ARDL

Short-Run Results				
Variables	Coeff	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob
$\Delta \ln GDP_{-1}$	0.2885**	0.0924	3.1235	0.0122
$\Delta \ln GDP_{-2}$	0.5201***	0.0998	5.2090	0.0006
$\ln \Delta K$	-0.0160	0.0114	-1.4050	0.1936
$\ln \Delta K_{-1}$	0.0245*	0.0116	2.1106	0.0640
$\ln \Delta K_{-2}$	0.0811***	0.0167	4.8413	0.0009
$\ln \Delta K_{-3}$	-0.0463***	0.0117	-3.9475	0.0034
$\ln \Delta L$	0.8268	0.8068	1.0249	0.3322
$\ln \Delta L_{-1}$	-3.4386***	0.8585	-4.0051	0.0031
$\ln \Delta L_{-2}$	-4.5130***	1.0982	-4.1092	0.0026
$\ln \Delta FDINDEX$	-8.4671***	2.4485	-3.4541	0.0072
$\ln \Delta FDINDEX_{-1}$	6.6652**	2.5208	-2.6441	0.0267
$\ln \Delta FDINDEX_{-2}$	-0.0856	0.0503	-1.6991	0.1235
$\ln \Delta FDINDEX_{-3}$	-0.1220**	0.0450	-2.4912	0.0343
$\ln \Delta GL$	-0.7164**	0.2984	-2.4006	0.0399
$\ln \Delta GL_{-1}$	-0.3496	0.2919	1.1975	0.2617
$\ln \Delta GL_{-2}$	-0.3369**	0.1484	-2.2684	0.0495
$\ln \Delta GL_{-3}$	-0.5579***	0.1208	-4.6180	0.0013
$\ln \Delta FD * \ln GL$	4.9502***	1.4274	3.4679	0.0071
$\ln \Delta FD * \ln GL_{-1}$	-3.9802**	1.4781	-2.6928	0.0247
ΔINF	-0.0002	0.0001	-1.6516	0.1330

ECM_{-1}	-0.9484***	0.0903	-10.4982	0.0000
R^2	0.9427			
Adjusted R^2	0.8711			

Note: *, implies 10% significance, ** implies 5% significance and *** implies 1% significance. The values in brackets are p-values.

The stability test for the model is presented in Figures 1 and 2. The blue lines in Figures 1 and 2 represent the CUSUM and CUSUMSQ lines, respectively, while the two red lines show the critical limit values at the 5% significance level. The obtained coefficients are stable when the blue line remains between the two red lines. The results show that the coefficients in our estimated models are stable, as the graph of CUSUM and CUSUMSQ statistics in Figures 1 and 2 respectively, lies in the critical bounds. The absence of divergence in CUSUM and CUSUMS graphs confirm that in our ARDL Models, long-run estimates are stable.

Source: Authors Computation

Figure 2 CUSUMSQ

Source: Authors Computation

The diagnostic test in Table 6 shows that the estimation is not undermined by the problems of autocorrelation, heteroscedasticity and ARDL functional form misspecification. This study arrived at this conclusion because the null hypothesis for all the tests is rejected. There is no serial correlation in the residuals of the ECM estimate. This shows that the model is valid and reliable.

Table 6 Diagnostic Tests

Test	F-statistics	Prob.
BPG Heteroskedasticity	0.9970	0.5386
BG Serial Correlation LM	3.0312	0.1199
Ramsey RESET	0.2336	0.6418
CUSUM	Stable	
CUSUMSQ	Stable	

4.5 Discussion of Findings

There is overwhelming evidence from all the estimations that FD harms EC in Nigeria both in the short-run and long-run. This finding aligns with some earlier studies in Nigeria and other economies (e.g., Adeniyi et al., 2015; Ductor and Grechyna, 2015; Akinlo, 2021; Yinusa et al., 2022; Elfaki and Ahmed, 2024). The possible reason why FD has a detrimental effect on EC in Nigeria might be due to excess money in the economy and overconcentration of financial resources in the financial sector. As stated by Santomero and Seater (2000) and Murphy et al. (1991), a rapidly growing financial sector draws most resources that ought to be distributed

among the different sectors and generates high rents; this is an example of suboptimal resource allocation that affects EC negatively. As a result, both short- and long-term EC are unattainable. The negative effect of FD on EC in Nigeria might also be due to misallocation of resources to unproductive projects by financial institutions due to asymmetric information or competition among financial institutions. Azibaraniyar (2023) found that misallocation of funds through financial management contributes to non-performing loans within the Nigerian banking sector. The study explained that financial mismanagement results in budget deficits, misallocation of resources, and reduced public trust which affect economic growth negatively. Competition among financial institutions to generate profits can result in oversupply of funds or misallocation of funds into unproductive projects or firms, thereby limiting EC. Murphy, Shleifer, and Vishny (1991) explained that FD can decrease EC if financial innovation discourages savings (i.e., dampening interest rates) and increases interest rates on investment funds.

An adverse connection is found between GL and EC in Nigeria. This finding corroborates the findings by Baidoo et al. (2023) and Duodu and Baidoo (2022), which focused on the Ghanaian economy; Polat et al. (2015), which focused on the South African economy; and Chibalamula et al. (2023), which considered underdeveloped countries. The negative connection between GL and EC is expected in Nigeria and possibly other developing countries. In the absence of proper planning, GL has the potential to exacerbate income inequality and expose a nation to fluctuations in capital and foreign trade. Nigeria is currently experiencing the biggest currency crisis and inflation because of its low productivity and reliance on imports. The economy is vulnerable to outside shocks and competition because of its reliance on the import of industrial goods, food, refined oil, and other necessities while exporting raw materials. Due to importation and the demand for foreign goods and services, the industrial sector has suffered greatly, which has increased unemployment and reduced government revenue. Due to its weak economic structure, underdeveloped banking sector, and inability to compete with wealthy nations in trade, Nigeria's economy is unable to fully benefit from GL. Similarly, study conducted by Iamsiraroj and Ulubaşoğlu (2015) have also shown that the benefits of GL are contingent upon the advancement of technology and the human capital progress in the host nation, both of which Nigeria currently lacks.

The Nigerian economy benefits from the interaction of FD and GL. This suggests that GL enhances the growth impact of FD in Nigeria. GL can attract FDI to the financial sector or enable financial institutions to have access to new sources of funds, which will boost their ability to make funds available for investment, according to Baldwin et al. (2005). Similarly, GL enables financial institutions to have access to modern technologies, which allows them to be more efficient in their operations while also reducing their cost of production. Through financial integration, GL can also strengthen the effect of FD on EC. The stability of the financial sector is improved by financial integration, which permits local and foreign financial institutions to share risks. The flood of investment from industrialised nations has given the financial sector access to more funds, making it more effective in funding capital projects and helping small businesses, both of which can spur EC. According to Tovar-Garcia (2012), financial GL makes foreign transactions less expensive. Low international transaction costs encourage effective capital allocation and strengthen the global connection between the financial and real sectors. By encouraging competition in the financial sector, GL can also strengthen the effect of FD on EC.

The National Bureau of Economic Research (2009) stated that greater financial GL would eventually result in a more efficient, transparent, and competitive financial industry. Efficiency in the delivery of financial services, the calibre of financial goods, and the level of innovation in the industry are all enhanced by a competitive financial sector, all of which are beneficial for EC. The financial sector may be able to process information more efficiently

owing to globalisation's facilitation of technological transfer. GL encourages technological spillovers and transfers, according to Skare and Soriano (2021). Technology has a favourable impact on the financial sector's performance through financial innovation, which can increase banks' ability to distribute risk and encourage resource efficiency, both of which enhance EC. The access to skilled labour through GL enables the financial institutions to employ competent labour with high marginal productivity, which enhances the output of the financial institutions.

The positive growth impact of the labour force in long-run suggests that human capital is a determinant of EC in Nigeria in the long-run. This finding supports the findings by Akinlo and Oyeleke (2020) and Nwaogu and Ikenyiri (2022). Also, the result for the labour force is in line with endogenous growth models, which contend that labour plays a significant role in a nation's long-term EC. However, the finding contradicts Mhaka and Taonezvi (2024), who found an insignificant relationship between labour and EC in SADC.

The negative effect of physical capital long-run suggests that resources are not efficiently allocated across the productive sector. The lack of capital investment in the real sector will affect employment levels and prevent additional investment opportunities that are required for economic expansion. Another possible reason why physical capital harms EG in the long-run might be due to capital flight. Akinlo (2024) stated that capital flight lowers investment, which in turn reduces output. Nigeria is currently battling a lack of funding for the investments required to support rapid EC. Inflation is found to exert a positive influence on EC in the long run, while it negatively impacts EC in the short-run. The effect of inflation on EC is mixed in literature. However, it has been argued that moderate inflation is not damaging to EC.

5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study examined how FD and GL directly affected EC in Nigeria between 1980 and 2023, as well as how they interacted. The study's short- and long-term outcomes were obtained using the ARDL model, and the long-term ARDL results were robustly checked using FMOLS and CCR approaches. The presence of long-term associations among the variables is also assessed using the ARDL cointegration bound test. The ARDL results show that FD and GL have detrimental effects on EC in Nigeria in both short-run and long-run, the interaction of FD with GL and the labour force enhanced EC in the long-run, physical capital produced a negative effect on EC in the long-run, inflation produces a positive effect on EC in the long-run but has no effect on EC in the short-run.

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Based on the estimated results from this study, first, the policymakers might need to target the increase in the production of goods and services in Nigeria through the provision of infrastructure, reduction in tariffs and investment in human capital. Targeting an increase in goods and services in which Nigeria has a comparative advantage like agriculture, textile, manufacturing, will boost exports and reduce imports. The low exports and high imports are one of the reasons why Nigeria could not maximise its benefits from globalisation. Similarly, Nigeria might need to tap the various natural resources that are lying idle to maximise the benefits from GL.

Second, the policymakers need to support the growth of the financial sector by providing physical and digital infrastructures to enhance the efficiency and reduce cost of production in the financial sector. Infrastructures will enable financial institutions to increase their services to remote areas and also enable them streamline transactions which will enhance their intermediation role in the economy.

Third, the complementary role of FD and GL found in this study indicates that policymakers must put policies in place that will ensure simultaneous growth of FD and GL. Any policy that targets the development of FD without GL and vice versa will counter growth for the economy since FD needs the inflow of technology, skilled manpower, foreign capital, etc. through GL to enhance EC. The policymakers may offer tax holidays or reduced corporate tax to attract foreign investors in fintech, digital banking and multinational banks to Nigeria.

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